

The Search for Relevance: A Context-Aware Paradigm Shift in Semantic and Task-Oriented V2X Communications

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Abstract—The design of communication systems has traditionally focused on the reliable and timely delivery of data. However, the scalability challenges faced by the evolution to a 6G-driven society demand new communication paradigms that carefully curate the content being transmitted. This paper envisions a joint semantic and task-oriented communication paradigm where Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) transmit only the information necessary to convey the desired meaning that is relevant to the intended receivers based on the communication context. The V2X domain offers a unique environment for the development of the envisioned semantic and task-oriented communications paradigm, as CAVs are native semantic devices, and the V2X domain is rich in contextual information. This contextual information can be leveraged to estimate the relevance that information may have for the intended receivers. We illustrate and quantitatively evaluate the potential benefits of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications. Numerical results show that by focusing on the transmission of the most relevant information for the intended receivers, semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can achieve a two-fold improvement in communication efficiency, which will significantly benefit the scalability of V2X networks.

Index Terms—semantic communication, task-oriented communication, V2X, 6G, relevance, context.

I. INTRODUCTION

THE advent of Vehicle-to-Everything (V2X) communications will drive the digital transformation of transportation systems and pave the way for a safer, more efficient, and more sustainable Cooperative, Connected, and Automated Mobility (CCAM). With V2X communications, Connected and Autonomous Vehicles (CAVs) will be able to exchange information through direct or network-based communications [1], enhancing their situational awareness, perception, and cooperative driving capabilities [2].

Like any existing communication system, current V2X communications prioritize the reliable and timely transmission of messages, addressing the technical communication problem identified by Shannon and Weaver at Level A [3]: “*how*

accurately can the communication symbols be transmitted?”. Level A is the first of three levels (A, B, and C) defined by Shannon and Weaver to systematically organize and analyze the broad subject of communication. A Level A-based design is agnostic to the content of the transmitted messages and it can result in the transmission of unnecessary information, ultimately wasting communication resources and potentially compromising communication efficiency and network scalability. Efficiency and scalability are set to be critical challenges in 6G and beyond, as the connectivity demand and the number of connected devices will continue to grow significantly. These challenges are particularly critical in V2X domain, where V2X-enabled CCAM applications will require CAVs to continuously broadcast rich information that demands substantial bandwidth. Current V2X networks are not ready to handle the large increase in data traffic that will result from the large-scale deployment of CAVs [4]. These challenges have recently prompted the design of communication systems that go beyond Level A, focusing on the content of the transmitted message and addressing the semantic and effectiveness communication problems formulated by Shannon and Weaver at Level B and Level C, respectively: “*how precisely do the transmitted symbols convey the desired meaning?*” (the semantic problem, Level B), and “*how effectively does the received meaning affect conduct in the desired way?*” (the effectiveness problem, Level C) [3].

Level B semantic communication systems have gained considerable attention in recent years because they can extract and transmit only the essential information needed to convey the meaning contained in specific data types such as text [5], audio [6], image [7], and video [8]. Most research in this area has focused on the Physical layer (PHY) layer, aiming to reduce the transmitted messages size beyond the limits of conventional lossless and lossy compression algorithms [9] by focusing on the exchange of meaning rather than mere data. However, semantic systems may require sophisticated and power-intensive AI-based techniques with high software, hardware,

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and energy demands which may challenge their deployment on resource-constrained connected devices.

Recent contributions attempting to address the Level C problem have focused on curating the content of the transmitted messages by optimizing metrics such as the Age of Information (AoI) [10], Age of Incorrect Information (AoII) [11], and Value of Information (VoI) [12]. These proposals rely on the assumption that these metrics can help identify the most important information for the intended receiver. However, metrics like AoI, AoII, and VoI are context-agnostic combinations of objective information attributes (e.g., freshness, quality, precision), while context is key to understand the meaning of the shared information and determine its impact on the intended receivers' behavior. In general, context refers to the circumstances or conditions surrounding a particular event. In the domain of machine-type communications, context includes information about the communication medium, the transmitter and receiver characteristics, the physical environment of the communication, and the actions and intentions of the communicating devices. Understanding the context in which information is exchanged is a complex task that requires processing rich contextual data. However, in most existing communication systems, connected devices do not typically share rich contextual information. Consequently, context often has to be reconstructed individually (and not cooperatively) by the transmitter [13], leading to partial and potentially inaccurate estimates.

This paper proposes a semantic and task-oriented¹ communication paradigm that jointly address the semantic (Level B) and effectiveness (Level C) problems by leveraging the concept of relevance. Relevance is a fundamental Level C attribute that intertwines the meaning of the information with the context in which it is exchanged to capture the impact that the context-dependent meaning of a piece of information has on the intended receiver's behavior or task [14]. In our vision, relevance is inherently context-dependent, and therefore, context must be a central and foundational element in the design of semantic and task-oriented communications. By focusing on relevance, semantic and task-oriented communications can transmit only the information necessary to convey the desired meaning that is relevant to the intended receivers and can influence their behavior. This approach jointly addresses the semantic and effectiveness problems by carefully selecting the content of transmitted messages based on its context-dependent relevance, avoiding the transmission of unnecessary (or irrelevant) information and improving communication efficiency and network scalability. We believe that the V2X domain provides a unique ecosystem for developing and deploying semantic and task-oriented V2X communications. First, CAVs are inherently semantic-native devices. They are equipped with powerful processors (multiple high-end CPUs and GPUs) and AI algorithms capable to semantically process data collected by onboard sensors and extract the most relevant information (e.g., lane margins, positions of surrounding

objects) needed for autonomous driving. Second, V2X communications provide the necessary rich contextual information, as vehicles must continuously share locally available data (e.g., their position, speed, and intended trajectory) and locally sensed data about the driving environment (e.g., the position of locally detected objects).

We qualitatively illustrate the potential of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications focusing on the cooperative perception use case. With cooperative perception, vehicles share information about objects locally detected by their onboard sensors to collectively enhance their driving environment awareness and improve driving safety. Several studies have shown that cooperative perception can challenge the scalability of V2X networks [15][16][17]. To this end, our qualitative analysis shows the potential of the envisioned semantic and task-oriented V2X communications paradigm to enhance the scalability of V2X networks. By focusing on transmitting only the most relevant information for the intended receivers, each vehicle can reduce the amount of information per transmitted message without compromising an accurate perception of the driving environment. These conclusions are supported by a quantitative analysis that compares the performance of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications with current V2X solutions. The comparison is conducted using a novel semantic evaluation framework introduced in this paper and tailored to the V2X domain, considering both unicast and broadcast communication scenarios. Our analysis shows that semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can increase the amount of relevant information transmitted to intended receivers by up to 36% while consuming less communication resources. Numerical results shows that semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can reduce the amount of resources consumed by each vehicle by up to 40% and can achieve an approximately two-fold improvement in communication efficiency.

The remainder of this paper is organized as follows. Section II reviews existing contributions in Level B and Level C semantic and task-oriented communications, with a focus on V2X. Section III elaborates on the core aspects of our semantic and task-oriented V2X vision. In Section IV, we provide a qualitative analysis of the potential of the semantic and task-oriented V2X communications paradigm within the context of cooperative perception. Section V introduces the semantic evaluation framework used for our quantitative analysis, while Section VI presents the numerical results. Finally, Section VII summarizes the conclusions and contributions of this paper.

II. RELATED WORK

The design of existing communication systems – including V2X – has traditionally been focused at Level A, and the majority of research efforts has concentrated on the design of solutions to guarantee the timely and reliable exchange of information with varying latency and reliability requirements. In V2X, these include the design of robust and flexible MAC

¹The terms task-oriented and goal-oriented communications are interchangeably used in the literature.

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and PHY layers, message generation rules that control the rate and size of the generated messages, and congestion and awareness control policies. However, the scalability challenges introduced by the increasing data demand and number of connected devices – including the large-scale deployment of CAVs – have recently pushed the design of communication systems beyond Level A, towards Level B and Level C.

Most contributions in Level B semantic communications operate at the PHY layer, primarily focusing on Joint Source-Channel Coding (JSCC). These proposals generally target the design of semantic compression techniques that can extract and transmit the semantic information embedded in specific data types such as text, audio, image, and video. In this context, semantic information refers to the essential set of features needed to convey the desired meaning of the exchanged information. For example, [5] introduces an end-to-end Transformer-based semantic communication system which can learn, extract, and transmit the essential semantic features of written text. A seminal contribution to semantic audio compression is presented in [6], where the authors extend their original work from [5] to introduce an end-to-end Deep Learning (DL)-based semantic communication system that employs 2D Convolutional Neural Networks (CNNs). The authors show that this system can effectively learn, extract, and transmit the semantic information of raw speech signals. Contributions in [7] and [8] address semantic compression for images and video. In [7], the authors present a DL-enabled semantic communication system featuring two matched CNNs connected within an end-to-end JSCC architecture, where the transmitter extracts and maps the critical spatial features of an image to a complex channel codeword. In [8], the authors address the design of a semantic video conferencing architecture using an end-to-end DL network that combines CNNs with hourglass networks to extract and transmit only crucial keypoints of video frames.

In the V2X domain, contributions in Level B semantic communications primarily focus on developing semantic compression techniques for image transmission, aiming to reduce the volume of information that vehicles exchange. For example, [9] compares the performance of semantic segmentation with lossy compression techniques, demonstrating that transmitting semantic information extracted from raw images can reduce network load, decrease end-to-end latency, and lower energy consumption. The contributions in [18] and [19] also make use of semantic segmentation. In [18], the authors design an autoencoder-based lossy compression technique that focuses image compression on regions of interest associated with semantically important classes, such as vehicles and trucks. The contribution in [19] presents an end-to-end Image Segmentation Semantic Communication (ISSC) system, designed to exchange only the essential semantic features present in the input image. In contrast, the work in [20] does not explicitly employ semantic segmentation. Instead, it presents a DL-based cooperative semantic communication system in which multiple transmitting vehicles collaboratively extract and share semantic information extracted from images.

Current proposals to address the effectiveness problem at Level C leverage the concepts of AoI, AoII, and VoI for designing task-oriented communication systems. AoI captures

the information freshness considering both the end-to-end transmission latency and the rate at which data is generated and received. In AoI-based systems, the content of transmitted messages is curated to minimize the AoI at the receiver, operating under the assumption that fresher information is more valuable for the receiver’s task [10]. AoII extends the AoI concept by combining the freshness of information and its informativeness [11]. Information is considered informative when it is not already known to the receiver. AoII-based systems assume that fresh and informative information is more valuable for the receiver’s task and prioritize its transmission.

Existing VoI definitions are highly task-dependent and encompass a broader range of attributes with respect to the AoI and AoII metrics. These attributes include, for example, information quality, precision, proximity, redundancy, freshness and informativeness. In the V2X domain, VoI-based communication systems use the VoI to determine what information vehicles should share. The study in [21] defines VoI as a weighted combination of proximity, timeliness, and quality of the information, with the specific weights adjusted according to the V2X use case. In [22], VoI for a remote driving task is defined as the reduction in path tracking error experienced by the receiving vehicle after correctly decoding a transmitted message. The study in [16] proposes a VoI definition based on relative entropy in the context of cooperative perception to decide which detected objects should be included in cooperative perception messages. Similarly, [17] introduces a VoI definition based on object dynamics, applying it to cooperative perception to transmit only the most dynamic detected objects, i.e., those with the greatest changes in speed, position, or heading. This approach is based on the premise that accurate perception of the driving environment requires more frequent updates on highly dynamic objects. Additional VoI definitions based on detected objects’ redundancy, perception quality, and classification confidence have recently been included in the cooperative perception standard [23] to regulate the amount of information shared by vehicles.

Existing Level C contributions have made important advances to improve V2X communications efficiency by curating the information shared by vehicles. However, the relevance of information is highly context-dependent, and the limitations of current Level C metrics become apparent, for example, when considering cooperative perception. For instance, a fresh (AoI [10]) and informative (AoII [11]) update about an unseen (entropy-based VoI [16]) and high-speed (dynamics-based VoI [17]) detected object may not be relevant to a receiving vehicle if the object is, for example, traveling in the opposite direction and has already passed the receiving vehicle. The importance to capture the context-dependence relevance of information is a central aspect of our semantic and task-oriented V2X communications vision.

III. A SEMANTIC AND TASK-ORIENTED V2X COMMUNICATIONS VISION

This paper proposes a semantic and task-oriented communications paradigm that jointly addresses the semantic (Level B) and effectiveness (Level C) problems by leveraging the concept of context-dependent relevance. By focusing on

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relevance, semantic and task-oriented communications can selectively transmit only the information necessary to convey the desired meaning that is relevant to the intended receivers under given context conditions. The V2X domain represents a unique environment for developing the envisioned semantic and task-oriented communications paradigm, as CAVs natively embed AI-based semantic processing capabilities and the V2X ecosystem is inherently rich of contextual information.

A. The Search for Relevance

As highlighted by linguists D. Wilson and D. Sperber in their relevance theory [14], the search for relevance is a key feature of human communication that enables the communication process to achieve the greatest possible efficiency with minimal effort. According to the relevance theory, relevance is defined as the impact that a piece of information has on the listener's perception of the world when processed within a context of existing assumptions. It is a non-binary concept that combines the intrinsic value and meaning of the information with the specific context in which the information is exchanged. In human communications, context consists of a complex multi-dimensional structure of relationships between contextual information elements that capture the temporal, spatial, social, psychological, and cultural dimensions of the interaction between speaker and listener [14][24]. We, as humans, are naturally endowed with the cognitive ability to grasp the context-dependent nature of information relevance and to understand the context (i.e., accurately identify its constituent relationships) by processing and interpreting the available contextual information. We naturally leverage the context to communicate only the most relevant information, thereby maximizing the efficiency of our interactions. Let's consider a simple example to illustrate how humans leverage context to communicate only the most relevant information. Two friends, Altea and Vicente, are at a party. Altea notices that Vicente, who is vegetarian, is holding an empty plate and says to him, "there is some salad in the kitchen". Altea is leveraging the context (Vicente's dietary preferences, his empty plate, and the location of the kitchen) to communicate only the most relevant information needed to convey the desired meaning and allow Vicente to find more food (i.e., accomplish his task or goal).

Inspired by the relevance theory, we believe that developing semantic and task-oriented communications where the search for relevance becomes a fundamental feature of machine-type communication is key for enhancing the efficiency of the data exchange and the scalability of future networks. To this end, we envision a semantic and task-oriented communication paradigm where connected devices are equipped with the necessary intelligence to understand the context and curate the exchanged information based on its context-dependent relevance for the intended receivers, much like humans do. In our vision, the concept of relevance directly stems from the definition provided by the relevance theory, but is extended from a Level C and task-oriented perspective to jointly address Level B and Level C problems. We define the relevance of a piece of information x as the context-dependent difference that the meaning of x yields on the receiver's digital representation of the world and, ultimately, on the receiver's task. Like in the relevance theory, this definition inherently depends on the

context of the interaction. We define context as a dynamic spatio-temporal structure of relationships between contextual information elements that describe the physical environment of the communication, the characteristics of the communication medium, the attributes of the transmitter and receiver, the actions and intentions of the communicating devices, and the information already available to the receiver. Focusing on the context-dependent relevance of the information represents a significant advancement over conventional metrics such as AoI, AoII, and VoI, as it can better capture the impact of the exchanged information on the receiver's task by contextualizing its meaning and attributes.

B. Semantic and Task-Oriented V2X Communications

In the V2X domain, relevance can be defined as the context-dependent impact that the meaning of a piece of information has on the receiving vehicle's digital representation of the driving environment and, ultimately, on its driving tasks. Relevance in the V2X domain is highly dependent on the context of the interaction. This is particularly evident in, for example, cooperative perception, where vehicles share information about objects detected through their onboard sensors. Properly contextualizing the meaning and attributes of local perception data is essential to accurately determine its relevance, as the relevance of a detected object for a receiving vehicle can vary significantly based on the context. Let's assume, for example, that the transmitting vehicle detects a pedestrian crossing an intersection using its onboard sensors. If the receiving vehicle is approaching the same intersection (context), the information about the pedestrian represents a safety-critical situation (meaning) that should be avoided (task) and its relevance is high, provided the information is accurate and timely (attributes). Conversely, if the receiving vehicle is leaving the intersection, the relevance of the meaning conveyed by the information about the pedestrian is low, regardless of its attributes.

Semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can prevent the transmission of unnecessary (or irrelevant) information and address the V2X scalability challenges that will arise with the large-scale deployment of CAVs. However, the design of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications faces unique challenges. First, the broadcast nature of V2X communications requires a multi-receiver design, where the relevance of the exchanged information is computed with respect to multiple – and not a single – intended receivers. This is a fundamental difference from other communication domains, which mainly rely on unicast communications (e.g., cellular networks). Second, the dynamism and complexity of connected and automated mobility hinder the accurate estimation of the context in which information is exchanged. This estimation is necessary to correctly determine the relevance of the information to be exchanged. However, a correct context understanding is rarely available explicitly in the exchanged contextual data and it requires AI-based processing algorithms that can interpret and predict in a manner similar to human cognition.

Despite existing challenges, the V2X domain represents a unique ecosystem for the realization and deployment of the

Fig. 1. Cooperative perception.

envisioned semantic and task-oriented V2X communications paradigm due to its native semantic processing capabilities and the inherent availability of rich contextual information. By design, the V2X domain functions as a native ISAC-type (Integrated Sensing and Communication) ecosystem, as CAVs cooperatively and continuously sense the surrounding environment (Sensing) and exchange locally generated information (Communication) about the driving environment and their own mobility. For example, vehicles continuously share data about their position and speed, detected objects (e.g., vehicles, vulnerable road users), and even their driving intentions (e.g., planned trajectories). This data can be further aggregated, refined, and complemented by the roadside V2X infrastructure, which can provide additional information such as traffic lights status and traffic conditions [2]. As a result, the V2X domain is inherently rich of contextual information about the physical communication environment, the characteristics of transmitters and receivers, as well as their actions and intentions. Another unique feature of the V2X domain is that the communicating devices – namely, the CAVs – are native semantic-based mobile platforms equipped with powerful hardware (CPUs and GPUs) and sophisticated AI algorithms. These capabilities are currently used by CAVs to semantically process raw data from onboard sensors and extract the most relevant information (e.g., lane margins, positions of surrounding objects) needed to plan and execute their driving maneuvers. In our vision, these hardware, software, and semantic processing capabilities can be leveraged by vehicles to process and interpret contextual information, accurately understand context, and identify the most relevant information for the intended receivers, paving the way for the development of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications.

IV. SEMANTIC AND TASK-ORIENTED V2X COMMUNICATIONS: AN ILLUSTRATIVE EXAMPLE WITH COOPERATIVE PERCEPTION

We illustrate the potential of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications considering the cooperative perception use case [23], also known as collective perception or sensor data sharing. Autonomous vehicles rely on a variety of onboard

sensors (e.g., lidars, radars, and cameras) to sense and locally collect information about the driving environment. However, the perception accuracy and range of onboard sensors can be limited by obstacles, adverse weather or challenging lighting conditions, and these limitations can significantly impact the driving safety. Cooperative perception addresses these limitations by allowing vehicles to share information about locally detected objects (e.g., vehicles and vulnerable road users) through V2X communications. This shared data is then combined with the information generated from onboard sensors, improving perception accuracy and extending the vehicles' perception range and field of view beyond the onboard sensors limits. By design, cooperative perception relies on the frequent exchange of locally detected objects to enhance the vehicles' perception capabilities and ensure they have the information necessary to safely drive.

Fig. 1 illustrates the operation of cooperative perception in an intersection scenario involving three communicating vehicles (V_1 , V_2 , and V_3) and six objects (x_k , $k = 1, \dots, 6$). In this scenario², we assume that all three vehicles are within V2X communication range and that there are no packet collisions or transmission errors. In Fig. 1(a), V_1 shares information with V_2 and V_3 about the three objects it has detected within its perception range (x_1 , x_2 , and x_3). In Fig. 1(b), V_2 reports to V_1 and V_3 about the four objects it has detected (x_1 , x_3 , x_4 and x_5). Similarly, in Fig. 1(c), V_3 informs V_1 and V_2 about the two objects it has detected (x_1 and x_6). Thanks to cooperative perception, all vehicles (V_1 , V_2 and V_3) receive information about all six objects in the scenario, even those outside the perception range of their onboard sensors. However, Fig. 1 also highlights some of the challenges and inefficiencies associated with cooperative perception, such as redundancy. In Fig. 1(c), all three vehicles transmit information about x_1 a total of $N_{tx} = 3$ times and information about x_3 a total of $N_{tx} = 2$ times via V2X communications. While some redundancy can be useful for confirming or cross-verifying local data, excessive redundancy can unnecessarily consume limited spectrum resources and compromise the scalability of V2X networks. Overloading the V2X network with redundant (and irrelevant) information may delay or block the transmission of relevant data, ultimately impacting the effectiveness of cooperative

² For simplicity, we assume that the detected objects reported by CAVs consists of only non-connected vehicles. In standardized cooperative

perception, CAVs report different types of non-connected objects (vehicles and other road users) and also other CAVs within their perception range.

(a) Transmitting CAV: V_1 . (b) Transmitting CAV: V_2 . (c) Transmitting CAV: V_3 .
Fig. 2. Cooperative perception with semantic and task-oriented V2X communications.

perception [15]. The example in Fig. 1 also highlights that current V2X communications can result in the transmission of non-redundant yet unnecessary (and irrelevant) information. For instance, the object x_2 , detected and transmitted by V_1 in Fig. 1(a), has low relevance for V_2 and V_3 since x_2 is leaving the intersection and does not influence V_2 , which is driving in the opposite direction, or V_3 , which is approaching the intersection. Similarly, the object x_5 transmitted by V_2 in Fig. 1(b) and the object x_6 transmitted by V_3 in Fig. 1(c) have minimal relevance for the respective receiving vehicles.

Cooperative perception relies on the frequent transmission of locally detected objects without considering their relevance to the receiving vehicles, which is inherently context-dependent. Fig. 2 illustrates how semantic and task-oriented V2X communications would impact cooperative perception by filtering the transmitted objects based on their context-dependent relevance to the intended receivers. In Fig. 2, each vehicle only transmits the objects that it deems relevant to the receiving vehicles. An object is considered relevant if it can influence the receivers' driving decisions. For example, in Fig. 2(a), V_1 transmits only objects x_1 and x_3 , as they are approaching the intersection and may impact the driving decisions of V_3 , which is also approaching the intersection. Although V_1 detects object x_2 , it does not report it, as it estimates it is not relevant for the intended receivers (V_2 and V_3) since x_2 is exiting the intersection and does not impact their mobility. Similarly, in Fig. 2(b), V_2 detects objects x_1 , x_3 , x_4 and x_5 but only transmits object x_4 . V_2 does not transmit objects x_1 and x_3 because they were already reported by V_1 , and redundant information is considered to be irrelevant in this example. Moreover, V_2 does not transmit x_5 since it is leaving the intersection and holds no relevance for V_3 (approaching the intersection) or V_1 (moving in the opposite direction), even if x_5 is not redundant. Similarly, V_3 does not transmit object x_6 in Fig. 2(c), as it estimates it irrelevant for both V_1 and V_2 due to their driving directions. V_3 also does not transmit object x_1 as it estimates it is redundant information for both V_1 and V_2 .

The comparison between Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 qualitatively highlights the potential advantages of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications in cooperative perception. In Fig. 1, vehicles transmit all locally detected objects regardless of their relevance for the intended receivers, with some information being transmitted multiple times ($N_{tx} > 1$). In

contrast, Fig. 2 shows that each vehicle only transmits information about the objects that are relevant to the driving decisions of its intended receivers. Semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can curate the content of the transmitted messages based on its context-dependent relevance, reducing the amount of transmitted data while ensuring that relevant information reaches the intended receivers. Consequently, semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can enhance the scalability of V2X networks and the effectiveness of the supported use cases. We should note that the potential advantages of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications are not confined to the cooperative perception context, and can be extended to other use cases such as cooperative awareness and cooperative driving. For the sake of brevity, we will refer to semantic and task-oriented V2X communications as semantic V2X communications in the rest of this work.

V. A SEMANTIC EVALUATION FRAMEWORK

A. Framework Definition

This Section introduces the semantic evaluation framework designed to quantify the potential of semantic communications in the V2X domain. The framework consists of a driving scenario of $W \times H$ m² with N CAVs, each denoted by V_n , $n = 1, \dots, N$. Without loss of generality, each vehicle V_n is randomly assigned a unique pair of origin-destination driving points within the scenario. We assume that for each origin-destination pair, there is a single path p_n that each vehicle can follow to reach its destination. The internal state of each vehicle V_n is denoted as s_n and we define s_n as a combination of endogenous and exogenous variables.

Endogenous variables (s_n^{end}) represent the intrinsic characteristics of the vehicle, such as its perception range, and all driving aspects directly controlled by the vehicle, including its position, speed, acceleration, destination and path p_n planned to reach the destination. Exogenous variables (s_n^{ex}) represent information available in the driving environment that is external to the vehicle, such as traffic lights status, road topology, and intended trajectories. In the context of cooperative perception, exogenous variables represent the objects in the driving environment (e.g., non-connected vehicles, vulnerable road users, and obstacles) and the information about these objects (e.g., their position, size, or

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speed). We define the set of exogenous variables available at V_n as:

$$s_n^{ex} = s_{n,loc}^{ex} \cup s_{n,V2X}^{ex}, \quad (1)$$

where $s_{n,loc}^{ex}$ represents the subset of exogenous variables collected locally by V_n using its onboard sensors, and $s_{n,V2X}^{ex}$ represents the subset of exogenous variables received by V_n from other vehicles via V2X communications.

Let \mathcal{K} denote the set of K exogenous variables available in the driving scenario, and let x_k , with $k = 1, \dots, K$, represent the k -th exogenous variable. We model the distribution of exogenous variables across the driving scenario using a 2D Poisson Point Process (PPP). We denote with $P(x_k \in s_{n,loc}^{ex})$ the probability that the exogenous variable x_k can be locally detected by V_n using its onboard sensors. In a cooperative perception context, $P(x_k \in s_{n,loc}^{ex})$ represents the detection probability, i.e., the probability that an object x_k is detected by V_n using its onboard sensors. This probability is modeled as a logistic function of $D_{k,n}$, the distance between x_k and V_n :

$$P(x_k \in s_{n,loc}^{ex}) = \frac{1}{1 + a_1 e^{-a_2(D_{k,n} - a_3)}}, \quad (2)$$

where a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 are fixed values.

In the semantic evaluation framework, the semantic value of an exogenous variable x_k is a measure of its context-dependent relevance. We define $f_n(\mathcal{K})$ as the contextual relevance function that models the relevance or semantic value of each exogenous variable x_k for each vehicle V_n . Without loss of generality, the contextual relevance function implemented in our framework is a discrete weighting function that assigns non-uniform semantic values $w_{n,k}$ to each exogenous variable x_k in \mathcal{K} . The semantic values are randomly sampled from either a low or high relevance set, and the assignment of an exogenous variable's semantic value $w_{n,k}$ to the low or high relevance set depends on each vehicle's planned path p_n . Exogenous variables with low relevance have a negligible semantic value, i.e., $w_{n,k} \cong 0$, and the fraction of low relevance variables to the total number of exogenous variables K is denoted by Δ_L . The semantic evaluation framework assumes that the contextual relevance function of two neighboring vehicles is correlated, with the correlation coefficient depending on the distance between vehicles. Additionally, a randomization factor p models the probability that the contextual relevance function of two neighboring vehicles is completely uncorrelated.

As in any driving scenario, an exogenous variable may be relevant (high semantic value) or irrelevant (low semantic value) for a vehicle, and the same variable could be highly relevant for one vehicle but irrelevant for another, depending on their context. The contextual relevance function $f_n(\mathcal{K})$ is designed to provide a simplified yet realistic representation of the context-dependent relevance that exogenous variables in the driving environment have for different vehicles. To illustrate this, Fig. 3 shows the contextual relevance function of vehicles V_2 and V_3 in the cooperative perception scenario depicted in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. In this scenario, both V_3 and object x_1 are approaching the intersection. Since the presence of x_1 can influence V_3 's driving decisions, x_1 is assigned a high semantic

value $w_{3,1}$ in the contextual relevance function of V_3 (see Fig. 3(a)), indicating that x_1 is highly relevant for V_3 . On the other hand, object x_2 is leaving the intersection and is not relevant for V_3 and its driving decisions. This is reflected in the low semantic value $w_{3,2}$ assigned to x_2 in V_3 's contextual relevance function (see Fig. 3(a)). The design of the contextual relevance function also captures how the relevance of detected objects depends on the different paths planned and followed by each vehicle. This is, for example, the case of the relevance of object x_1 for V_3 and V_1 in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2. V_1 has already passed x_1 and is moving in the opposite direction, making x_1 irrelevant for V_1 . Conversely, x_1 is highly relevant for V_3 because they are both approaching the intersection. The distance-based correlation between contextual relevance functions of two different vehicles models the probability that a detected object (i.e., an exogenous variable) is similarly relevant for two neighboring vehicles experiencing similar driving conditions, for example, driving in the same direction. This would be the case for vehicles V_2 and V_3 in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 if V_3 decides to turn right at the intersection. The randomization factor p accounts for the probability that a detected object has completely different relevance for two neighboring vehicles, for example, when they are traveling in opposite directions. For example, in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2, object x_1 (approaching the intersection) is highly relevant for V_3 (also approaching the intersection), which is reflected in Fig. 3(a). However, it has a low relevance for V_2 (leaving the intersection) as shown in Fig. 3(b), despite the close proximity between V_2 and V_3 .

Fig. 3. Contextual relevance function $f_n(\mathcal{K})$ design.

In the semantic evaluation framework, vehicles use time-slotted V2X communications to exchange the exogenous variables locally detected through their onboard sensors. The goal of the communication is to provide the intended receivers with the most relevant collected information about the driving environment. Relevant information is the information with a context-dependent meaning that can influence the safety or driving maneuvers of the intended receiver. Without loss of generality, we assume that redundant information does not have any impact on the intended receiver's understanding of the driving environment (i.e., is irrelevant) and, therefore, its semantic value is always equal to zero. We also assume that there are no transmission errors or packet collisions. Vehicles take turns accessing the channel and in each time slot, each vehicle can be in one of two possible states: Transmit or Receive.

In the Transmit state, the transmitting vehicle (V_T) first updates its set of locally collected exogenous variables ($s_{T,loc}^{ex}$)

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based on $P(x_k \in s_{T,loc}^{ex})$. $P(x_k \in s_{T,loc}^{ex})$ is the probability that the exogenous variable x_k can be locally detected by V_T using its onboard sensors, and this probability is modelled as a function of $D_{k,T}$, the distance between V_T and the exogenous variable x_k . Then, V_T generates a V2X message that includes its own position and speed (i.e., its endogenous variables s_T^{end}) and a selected subset $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|$ of the locally collected exogenous variables $s_{T,tx}^{ex}$ (where $s_{T,tx}^{ex} \subset s_{T,loc}^{ex}$). In the semantic evaluation framework, the number of exogenous variables included in each message $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|$ must comply with some communication constraint Γ . Γ represents the maximum number of exogenous variables that each vehicle can transmit in a message. The number of transmitted exogenous variables is a proxy of the message size and Γ represents the network-level communication constraint that can be enforced by V2X congestion control mechanisms to keep the V2X network load below pre-defined thresholds. If $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|$ exceeds Γ , the subset of exogenous variables included in the generated message is filtered according to the communication schemes described in the following section to meet the constraint Γ .

In the Receive state, the receiving vehicle (V_R) decodes the message transmitted by V_T and updates the subset of exogenous variables received via V2X communications ($s_{R,V2X}^{ex}$) with the received information, i.e., $s_{T,tx}^{ex}$. We assume that the information received from a transmitting vehicle expires after N slots, meaning it is valid only until the same transmitting vehicle transmits a new set of locally collected exogenous variables in the next communication cycle. At each vehicle, a communication cycle is defined as the time interval between two consecutive transmission attempts.

B. V2X Communication Schemes

We leverage the semantic evaluation framework to analyze and compare the performance of five distinct V2X communication schemes: baseline, inclusion rate control, redundancy mitigation, semantic, and ideal semantic. V2X schemes affect the selection of the exogenous variables included in each transmitted message and, therefore, can significantly influence the scalability of V2X networks and the efficient accomplishment of the communication's goal: delivering the most relevant driving environment information to the intended receivers.

1) Baseline

The baseline scheme attempts to include all locally collected exogenous variables ($s_{T,loc}^{ex}$) in the generated messages ($s_{T,tx}^{ex} = s_{T,loc}^{ex}$), like in Fig. 1. If the number of locally detected exogenous variables exceeds Γ , the number of exogenous variables included in the message ($s_{T,tx}^{ex}$) must be reduced to meet the limit imposed by Γ . In this case, the baseline scheme randomly selects Γ variables from the detected $s_{T,loc}^{ex}$ variables.

2) Inclusion Rate Control (IRC)

Inclusion rate control is part of the cooperative perception standard message generation rules [23]. It removes the amount of redundant information needed to guarantee that the size of the generated messages complies with the communication constraints. In the semantic evaluation framework, the IRC

scheme initially attempts to include all locally collected exogenous variables in the generated message. If the number of variables in the generated message ($s_{T,tx}^{ex}$) is larger than the constraint Γ , the IRC scheme removes redundant variables until $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}| = \Gamma$, i.e., until the constraint is met. Redundant exogenous variables are estimated by the transmitter by monitoring the information exchanged on the V2X network and assuming that the content of any message it can decode is also available at other vehicles. If the number of exogenous variables in the generated message exceeds Γ after removing all redundant exogenous variables, a random selection of Γ non-redundant exogenous variables is included in the transmitted message.

3) Redundancy Mitigation (RM)

Redundancy mitigation was originally proposed in the context of cooperative perception to avoid the transmission of redundant information and improve the scalability of V2X networks [15], but it can be applied to other scenarios. The RM scheme implemented in our framework includes in a message the set of locally collected exogenous variables ($s_{T,loc}^{ex}$) that are not redundant. Redundant variables are estimated following the same approach of the IRC scheme. Like for the baseline and IRC scheme, the number of exogenous variables included in a message cannot exceed the communication constraint Γ . If it does, a random selection of Γ non-redundant exogenous variables is included in the transmitted message.

4) Semantic

In line with the proposed vision, we have implemented a semantic V2X communication scheme that selects the locally collected exogenous variables ($s_{T,loc}^{ex}$) for transmission based on their context-dependent relevance to the intended receivers (\mathcal{R}). The transmitting vehicle uses a semantic model to curate the set of transmitted exogenous variables ($s_{T,tx}^{ex}$) based on the relevance $\mathcal{S}_R(x_k)$ of each exogenous variable for each intended receiver. A semantic model is a tool that processes available contextual information to provide an estimate $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k)$ of the context-dependent relevance of each exogenous variable (x_k) for each intended receiver ($R \in \mathcal{R}$).

In the semantic evaluation framework, the available contextual information consists of the intended receiver's position and speed (i.e., its endogenous variables \hat{s}_R^{end}) and all the exogenous variables exchanged over the V2X network by the communicating vehicles. To confine the framework's complexity, we assume that the semantic model can estimate the intended receiver's planned path (p_R) by tracking its position and speed (contextual information); vehicles include this information in their transmitted messages (Section V-A). The semantic model leverages the estimated planned path of the intended receiver to estimate its contextual relevance function $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$. To capture realistic conditions, we assume that the estimation of the contextual relevance function $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$ is non-ideal, and the $\hat{w}_{R,k}$ estimates are subject to an estimation error ε . We assume that the transmitter can reduce the estimation error ε and improve the accuracy of the $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$ estimate as it collects more contextual information (exogenous variables)

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from the driving environment (i.e., as $|s_{T,t}^{ex}|$ increases). As illustrated in Fig. 4, we model the semantic value $\hat{w}_{R,k}$ assigned by the contextual relevance function estimate $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$ as a uniform random variable within an estimation interval containing the true value $w_{R,k}$. The interval's width is $\delta(\varepsilon) = (\max(w_{R,k}) - \min(w_{R,k})) \cdot \varepsilon$. In the semantic evaluation framework, we model the estimation error ε , and hence $\delta(\varepsilon)$, using a logistic function:

$$\varepsilon = \frac{1}{1 + a_4 e^{-a_5(|s_{T,t}^{ex}| - a_6)}}, \quad (3)$$

where a_4 , a_5 , and a_6 are fixed values.

Fig. 4. Imperfect estimation of the semantic value $\hat{w}_{R,k}$ in the estimated $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$ of an intended receiver.

The semantic model processes contextual information, including the exogenous variables that vehicles transmit in their V2X messages. Like the IRC and RM schemes, the semantic scheme monitors the information exchanged over the V2X network to estimate which exogenous variables are already available at the intended receiver (\hat{s}_R^{ex}) and to identify redundant information. The semantic model assigns a semantic value $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k)$ of zero to redundant exogenous variables, as it estimates that transmitting again these exogeneous variables would not improve the intended receiver's understanding of the driving environment, making them irrelevant. On the other hand, the semantic model estimates the semantic value $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k)$ of non-redundant exogenous variables equal to $\hat{w}_{R,k}$ from the estimated contextual relevance function $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$.

The semantic scheme leverages the estimate $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k)$ provided by the semantic model to select only the most relevant exogenous variables to include in the generated messages. The selection aims to maximize the relevance (or semantic value) of the generated messages while respecting the communication constraint Γ and avoiding the transmission of irrelevant information. The relevance-aware operation of the semantic scheme can be expressed analytically as:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{T,t}^{ex} &= \arg \max_{x_k \in s_{T,loc}^{ex}} \max_{R \in \mathcal{R}} \hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k) \\ \text{s.t. } &\max_{R \in \mathcal{R}} \hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k) > \mathcal{S}_{min} \\ &|s_{T,t}^{ex}| < \Gamma, \end{aligned} \quad (4)$$

where \mathcal{S}_{min} is a relevance threshold that distinguishes between sufficiently relevant and irrelevant information. The operation of the semantic scheme can be summarized as follows. First, it estimates the relevance of the locally available exogenous variables using the semantic model and compares them against the minimum relevance threshold \mathcal{S}_{min} . Exogenous variables with a relevance (or semantic value) below the \mathcal{S}_{min} threshold

are filtered out and not included in the transmitted messages. Then, it ranks the available exogenous variables based on their relevance and selects the most relevant Γ variables. Unlike its baseline, IRC, and RM counterparts, the semantic scheme takes into account the communication constraint Γ during the content selection phase, and avoids the random filtering of the generated messages content.

5) Ideal Semantic

The ideal semantic scheme represents an ideal and benchmark implementation of the envisioned semantic and task-oriented V2X communication paradigm. Similar to the semantic scheme, the ideal semantic scheme uses the semantic model to identify and transmit only the most relevant exogenous variables while respecting the communication constraint Γ and avoiding the transmission of irrelevant information. However, in the ideal semantic case, we assume that the semantic model can perfectly estimate the contextual relevance function $\hat{f}_R(\mathcal{K})$ of each intended receiver ($R \in \mathcal{R}$). In other words, we assume that the error of the semantic model represented in Fig. 4 is zero, meaning the transmitting vehicle perfectly knows the semantic value $w_{R,k}$ assigned by each intended receiver to the exogenous variables x_k . In the ideal semantic case, we also assume that the semantic model can perfectly estimate the internal state (s_R) of the intended receivers, allowing it to perfectly identify the set of exogenous variables already available at each intended receiver, i.e., the redundant information. As a result, the semantic model provides a perfect estimate $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k) = \mathcal{S}_R(x_k)$ of the relevance (or semantic value) of each exogenous variables x_k for each intended receiver $R \in \mathcal{R}$. The operation of the ideal semantic scheme can be represented analytically as follows, where the estimated relevance $\hat{\mathcal{S}}_R(x_k)$ in (4) is replaced with its actual value $\mathcal{S}_R(x_k)$:

$$\begin{aligned} s_{T,t}^{ex} &= \arg \max_{x_k \in s_{T,loc}^{ex}} \max_{R \in \mathcal{R}} \mathcal{S}_R(x_k) \\ \text{s.t. } &\max_{R \in \mathcal{R}} \mathcal{S}_R(x_k) > \mathcal{S}_{min} \\ &|s_{T,t}^{ex}| < \Gamma. \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

The operation of the ideal semantic scheme follows the same operational steps as its semantic counterpart but replacing estimates with actual values.

VI. NUMERICAL EVALUATION

This Section presents a numerical evaluation of the potential of semantic V2X communications to efficiently and scalably accomplish the communication goal: provide the intended receivers with the most relevant driving environment information. To do so, this Section compares the performance of the five V2X communication schemes outlined in Section V.B: *Baseline*, *Inclusion Rate Control (IRC)*, *Redundancy Mitigation (RM)*, *Semantic*, and *Ideal Semantic*.

Unless otherwise specified, we consider a driving scenario of 800 x 200 m² with a total of $|K| = 110$ exogenous variables. The local perception range of each vehicle is set equal to 150 m by configuring the coefficients a_1 , a_2 , and a_3 in (2) to 0.08, -0.08,

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and 60, respectively. The local perception range is defined as the distance at which the probability $P(x_k \in s_{n,loc}^{ex})$ of locally detecting an exogenous variable x_k reaches zero. Vehicles are capable of communicating in either unicast or broadcast mode and, without loss of generality, we assume an ideal V2X communication channel, meaning that all transmitted messages are correctly decoded by the receivers. We consider that only 30% of the of the $|K|$ exogenous variables are highly relevant ($\Delta_L = 0.7$). Low-relevance variables are assigned a semantic value $w_{n,k}$ of 0, while the semantic value of high-relevance variables is randomly sampled from the range $[0.5, 1]$. The contextual relevance functions of two neighbouring vehicles are correlated with a probability p equal to 0.5. The correlation coefficient depends on the distance between the vehicles. The coefficient is set to 0.9 when the distance is less than 100 m, and linearly decreases to zero at a distance of 400 m. The coefficients a_4 , a_5 , and a_6 in (3) that define the semantic model's estimation error ε are set to 1, -0.5, and 26.

A. Unicast

We first consider a unicast scenario with $N = 2$ communicating CAVs. Fig. 5 compares the capability of the five V2X schemes to achieve the communication goal, namely, conveying the relevant information to the intended receiver. The figure reports the High-Relevance variables Ratio (HRR) as a function of the communication constraint Γ . The HRR measures the ratio between the number of high-relevance exogenous variables available at each vehicle and the total number of high-relevance exogenous variables $|K|$ available in the driving scenario. The considered Γ values range from an extremely resource-constrained communication scenario ($\Gamma = 1$) to an unconstrained scenario ($\Gamma = 25$ in our scenario) where the number of exogenous variables locally detected by each vehicle is always lower than Γ and CAVs can transmit them all. Fig. 5 shows that the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* V2X schemes provide the intended receiver with a larger fraction of high-relevance exogenous variables compared to the *Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM* schemes. Existing V2X schemes (*Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM*) can only achieve HRR values similar to the semantic schemes when the communication constraints Γ are relaxed, i.e., when the communication bandwidth is not restricted and vehicles can transmit information about a larger set of exogeneous variables. In contrast, the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* V2X schemes can provide a large fraction of high-relevance exogeneous variables even when Γ is low. These results underscore the potential of semantic V2X communications to improve the communication efficiency and convey the most relevant information to the intended receiver also in resource-constrained scenarios. The comparison between the *Semantic* and *Ideal Semantic* shows that the benefits of semantic V2X communications depend on the vehicles' capability to accurately estimate the contextual relevance function of their intended receiver. Nevertheless, Fig. 5 shows that semantic V2X communication significantly outperforms existing V2X schemes (*Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM*), even with imperfect estimations (*Semantic*). In addition, Fig. 5

shows that the *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* V2X schemes exhibit similar performance across all values of Γ . These results indicate that simply avoiding (*RM*) or reducing (*IRC*) the transmission of redundant information does not necessarily ensure that the intended receiver receives the most relevant information. Consequently, redundancy mitigation schemes alone can only partially address the scalability challenges of future V2X networks.

Fig. 5. HRR. Unicast scenario.

The capability of the V2X schemes to accomplish the communication goal and transmit the most relevant information to the intended receiver (Fig. 5) directly stems from their capability to semantically curate the content of transmitted messages. Fig. 6(a) presents the average semantic value (\overline{SV}) of the messages transmitted by each of the five V2X schemes. \overline{SV} represents the sum of the semantic value $S_R(x_k)$ of each exogenous variable $x_k \in s_{T,tx}^{ex}$ included in the transmitted message. As noted in Section V-A, the semantic value of an exogenous variable x_k is zero if x_k is already available at the intended receiver (i.e., it is redundant) and equal to its context-dependent semantic value $w_{R,k}$ otherwise. Fig. 6(a) shows that the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes include more relevant information in their transmitted messages, achieving higher \overline{SV} values than the *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes. The *Semantic* scheme achieves lower \overline{SV} values than the *Ideal Semantic* as its estimate of the intended receiver's contextual relevance function is not entirely accurate. Reducing the semantic model's estimation error is key to unlock the full potential of semantic V2X communications. Additionally, Fig. 6(a) shows that relevance-agnostic schemes (*RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline*) are particularly ineffective at ensuring the transmission of relevant content (i.e., with high semantic value) under low-medium Γ values or stringent communication constraints. These schemes do not filter exogeneous variables based on their relevance to the intended receiver and may attempt to transmit a number of variables $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|$ that exceeds the communication constraint Γ . In this case, vehicles can transmit only Γ variables and these variables are randomly selected among the locally detected ones. The random filtering can inadvertently exclude exogeneous variables with high relevance or semantic value, as highlighted in Fig. 6(a). The importance of semantically curating the content of the transmitted messages decreases when Γ exceeds the average number of locally detected exogeneous variables $|s_{n,loc}^{ex}|$. The value of $|s_{n,loc}^{ex}|$ is 15 in our

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scenario. In this case, the available bandwidth is sufficient to transmit all locally detected variables, and the semantic selection of these variables has no impact on the average semantic value \overline{SV} .

Fig. 6(a) shows that existing V2X schemes (*Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM*) can achieve the same average semantic value \overline{SV} as the *Semantic* scheme when the communication constraint Γ is relaxed. However, this is accomplished with a much less efficient use of the communication channel. Fig. 6(b) reports the Low-Relevance Ratio (LRR) metric, which measures the fraction of irrelevant or low-relevance exogenous variables included in each transmitted message, as a function of the communication constraint Γ . In this study, an exogenous variable is considered irrelevant if its context-dependent semantic value is below a threshold \mathcal{S}_{min} , set at 0.05. Fig. 6(b) shows that the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes consistently outperform the *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes across all values of Γ . The semantic schemes consistently transmit a much smaller fraction of irrelevant variables, resulting in a more efficient use of communication bandwidth. This holds true even for Γ values equal to or greater than 20, which is the threshold at which the *Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM* schemes reach the same average semantic value \overline{SV} as the *Semantic* scheme in Fig. 6(a). However, they do so at a significantly higher communication cost, as *Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM* transmit a considerably larger fraction of irrelevant variables.

Fig. 6. \overline{SV} (a) and LRR (b). Unicast scenario.

Fig. 6(b) further highlights the importance of improving the estimate of the contextual relevance function of the intended receiver to unlock the full potential of semantic communications. The figure shows that the *Ideal Semantic* scheme consistently achieves LRR values of zero across all Γ values by perfectly identifying and filtering irrelevant information. Although the *Semantic* scheme significantly reduces LRR compared to the *Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM* schemes, it cannot bring LRR to zero due to an imperfect estimation of the contextual relevance functions. These inaccuracies prevent the *Semantic* scheme from identifying all low-relevance exogenous variables, leading it to transmit more irrelevant information than the *Ideal Semantic* scheme despite achieving comparable values of HRR (Fig. 5) and \overline{SV} (Fig. 6(a)). These results demonstrate that the efficiency of semantic V2X communications strongly depends on accurately estimating the

relevance of the information for the intended receiver.

By prioritizing the transmission of the most relevant information, the semantic schemes increase the average semantic value of transmitted messages (Fig. 6(a)) and reduce the number of transmitted variables. This is illustrated in Fig. 7(a), which presents the average number of exogenous variables x_k per transmitted message ($|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|$, a proxy of the message size), normalized with respect to the communication constraint Γ . The ratio $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|/\Gamma$ represents the communication resources' usage or the fraction of available communication resources utilized by each scheme to transmit each message. Fig. 7(a) demonstrates that the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes significantly reduce the number of transmitted variables compared to existing schemes (*Baseline*, *IRC*, and *RM*) by focusing on the transmission of the most relevant variables. This approach reduces bandwidth consumption and enhances communication efficiency. In contrast, the *Baseline* and *IRC* schemes consume – and waste – the largest amount of resources. The *Baseline* scheme attempts to transmit all locally detected exogenous variables and the *IRC* scheme removes only the subset of redundant variables needed to meet the constraint Γ . With respect to the *Baseline* and *IRC* schemes, the *RM* scheme reduces bandwidth consumption by filtering out all redundant variables. However, non-redundant variables can still be irrelevant, preventing *RM* from achieving the performance levels of semantic schemes. Consequently, *RM* transmits 3.9 and 1.6 times more exogenous variables than the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes, respectively, when $\Gamma > 20$ (Fig. 7(a)). The *Semantic* scheme cannot reach the values of $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|/\Gamma$ obtained with *Ideal Semantic* due to its imperfect estimation of the contextual relevance function of the intended receiver, which leads to the transmission of irrelevant variables (Fig. 6(b)).

Fig. 7. $|s_{T,tx}^{ex}|/\Gamma$ (a) and SE (b). Unicast scenario.

Fig. 5 through Fig. 7(a) numerically demonstrate the unique benefits of semantic V2X communications. Semantic communications enable the transmission of a larger amount of relevant information to the intended receiver (Fig. 5), increase the semantic value of transmitted messages (Fig. 6(a)), and reduce the number of transmitted exogenous variables (Fig. 6(b) and Fig. 7(a)). In essence, these results demonstrate that semantic V2X communications can accomplish the communication goal more efficiently. Fig. 7(b) compares the

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efficiency of the five schemes reporting the Semantic Efficiency (SE) as a function of Γ . SE measures the average semantic value that is conveyed by each transmitted exogenous variable. This metric provides an indication of the communication efficiency as it captures the amount of resources that need to be consumed by each vehicle to convey the desired meaning that is relevant to the intended receiver. A lower SE means that vehicles must transmit a larger number of exogenous variables to accomplish the communication goal. Fig. 7(b) shows that, by focusing on the transmission of the most relevant information, semantic V2X schemes can augment the semantic efficiency with respect to relevance-agnostic schemes (*RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline*), and optimize the bandwidth consumption. In particular, *Semantic* achieves a two-fold improvement in terms of semantic efficiency with respect to the *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes for all considered values of Γ . *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes achieve a similar SE across all Γ values, which indicates that avoiding (*RM*) or reducing (*IRC*) the transmission of redundant information is not sufficient to efficiently convey the desired meaning that is relevant to the intended receiver. The gap between the *Semantic* and *Ideal Semantic* schemes shows the importance of an accurate estimation of the contextual relevance function to improve the communication efficiency.

Fig. 8. (a) HRR. Broadcast scenario. (b) Semantic model's estimation error ϵ .

B. Broadcast

We now analyze a broadcast communication scenario with $N = 4$ communicating CAVs. Fig. 8(a) compares the fraction of high-relevance exogenous variables available at each vehicle (HRR) in the broadcast scenario. The figure shows that, like in the unicast scenario (Fig. 5), the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes transmit more relevant exogenous variables than the *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes, particularly at lower Γ values. At low Γ values, the *Semantic* scheme improvement with respect to relevant-agnostic schemes can be as large as 36%. These lower Γ values represent more constrained communication conditions, where a careful selection of transmitted information is crucial. The comparison between Fig. 5 and Fig. 8(a) reveals that an increase in the number of communicating CAVs particularly benefits the *Semantic* scheme, which achieves HRR values very close to the *Ideal Semantic* benchmark. As the number of communicating vehicles increases, the amount of contextual information

exchanged over the V2X network also rises. This additional contextual information enables a more accurate understanding of the communication context, thereby reducing the semantic model's estimation error ϵ . This trend is evident in Fig. 8(b), which compares the estimation error ϵ in unicast and broadcast scenarios as a function of Γ . The figure shows a notable reduction in ϵ in the broadcast scenario, which improves the estimation of the intended receivers' contextual relevance function and explains why *Semantic* approaches the *Ideal Semantic*'s performance in Fig. 8(a).

The trends observed in Fig. 8(b) also explain the improvement in the average semantic value \overline{SV} of the *Semantic* scheme in the broadcast scenario (Fig. 9(a)) compared to the unicast scenario (Fig. 6(a)). Fig. 9(a) compares the \overline{SV} performance of the different V2X schemes in the broadcast scenario. By reducing the semantic model's estimation error, the *Semantic* scheme can better identify the most relevant exogenous variables and maximize the semantic value of transmitted messages in the broadcast scenario, achieving nearly the same \overline{SV} performance as the *Ideal Semantic* benchmark. Fig. 9(a) also shows that the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes achieve higher \overline{SV} values compared to the relevance-agnostic *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes in the broadcast scenario. Additionally, Fig. 9(a) reveals that increasing the number of communicating CAVs significantly deteriorates the \overline{SV} performance of the *Baseline* and *IRC* schemes, especially at large Γ values, due to increased redundancy levels. A larger number of communicating vehicles increases the likelihood that an exogenous variable x_k is redundantly detected by multiple vehicles due to overlapping local perception ranges. For the *Baseline* and *IRC* schemes, this leads to a higher probability that the transmitting vehicles include exogenous variables already available at the intended receivers, i.e., that are redundant. Recall that the *IRC* scheme does not remove all redundant variables from the transmitted messages, but only the subset needed to comply with the communication constraint Γ . The transmission of redundant exogenous variables reduces the semantic value per transmitted message, as the semantic value of a redundant exogenous variable x_k is zero in the adopted semantic evaluation framework.

Fig. 9. \overline{SV} (a) and LRR (b). Broadcast scenario.

The reduction of ϵ observed in Fig. 8(b) also explains the reduction in LRR achieved by *Semantic* in the broadcast

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scenario (Fig. 9(b)) with respect to the unicast scenario (Fig. 6(b)). The *Semantic* scheme can achieve a more accurate estimate of the intended receivers' contextual relevance function in the broadcast scenario, and this helps it better identify the relevant (Fig. 9(a)) and irrelevant exogenous variables (Fig. 9(b)). We should note that *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* also reduce the LRR in the broadcast scenario compared to unicast (0.7 to 0.43). This is because an exogenous variable is considered irrelevant in the broadcast scenario only when its semantic value is below \mathcal{S}_{min} for all intended receivers.

Fig. 10(a) analyzes the normalized average number of exogenous variables per transmitted message ($|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$) in the broadcast scenario. Comparing Fig. 7(a) (unicast) and Fig. 10(a) (broadcast) reveals that increasing the number of communicating vehicles positively impacts the *Semantic* scheme's $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ performance. A larger number of transmitting vehicles improves the estimation of contextual relevance functions, and this helps the *Semantic* scheme to include only the most relevant exogenous variables in each message. For example, the $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ values achieved by the *Semantic* scheme at $\Gamma = 10$ and $\Gamma = 15$ decrease from 0.79 to 0.66 and from 0.55 to 0.45, respectively, when moving from the unicast to the broadcast scenario. Additionally, the gap in $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ between the *Semantic* and *Ideal Semantic* schemes is significantly reduced in Fig. 10(a), highlighting that semantic V2X can positively exploit an increasing number of communicating vehicles to optimize the message content. Note that the *Ideal Semantic* scheme exhibits higher $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ values in the broadcast scenario (Fig. 10(a)) than in the unicast one (Fig. 7(a)). For example, at $\Gamma = 10$ and $\Gamma = 15$, the *Ideal Semantic* scheme's $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ performance increases from 0.35 to 0.58 and from 0.23 to 0.39, respectively, when moving from unicast (Fig. 7(a)) to broadcast (Fig. 10(a)) communications. This occurs because broadcast communications involve a higher number of intended receivers, each with a different contextual relevance function. As a result, the *Ideal Semantic* scheme must include a larger set of exogenous variables in each transmitted message to ensure all the intended receivers obtain the most relevant information. The sensitivity of $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ to the number of intended receivers in broadcast communications (Fig. 10(a)) is not exclusive to the *Ideal Semantic* scheme but is an intrinsic characteristic of all semantic schemes. Fig. 10(a) also shows that *RM* reduces the $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ in the broadcast scenario, and augments its difference with the *IRC* and *Baseline* schemes. *RM* reduces the number of variables per transmitted message thanks to the increased redundancy levels experienced in the broadcast scenario. Nevertheless, the *RM* scheme cannot achieve the performance levels of the *Semantic* scheme. The performance gap between *RM* and *Semantic* scheme remains quite significant, with the *Semantic* scheme reducing the consumption of communication resources by up to 40%. The sensitivity of the *Ideal Semantic* scheme to the number of intended receivers increases the average number of exogenous variables per transmitted message in the broadcast scenario,

reducing its communication efficiency. This effect is evident when comparing the semantic efficiency between the unicast (Fig. 7(b)) and broadcast (Fig. 10(b)) scenarios, with the *Ideal Semantic* average SE levels decreasing by approximately 50% in the broadcast scenario. In contrast, an increase in the number of communicating vehicles is especially beneficial for the *Semantic* scheme. With more contextual information available, the semantic model's estimation error decreases in the broadcast scenario, allowing the *Semantic* scheme to more accurately identify the most relevant exogenous variables and maximize the semantic value of the transmitted messages, while also reducing the number of exogenous variables per message. Improvements in \overline{SV} and $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ performance offset the negative effects associated with the sensitivity of the *Semantic* scheme to the number of intended receivers, and its SE performance is not deteriorated in the broadcast scenario (Fig. 10(b)). The positive impact of an increasing number of communicating vehicles on the performance of *Semantic* is further demonstrated by the significant reduction in the SE gap between the *Semantic* and *Ideal Semantic* schemes when moving from the unicast (Fig. 7(b)) to the broadcast scenario (Fig. 10(b)).

Fig. 10. $|\overline{s_{T,tx}^{ex}}|/\Gamma$ (a) and SE (b). Broadcast scenario.

The sensitivity of the semantic schemes to the number of intended receivers does not diminish their efficiency advantage over the relevance-agnostic *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes when transitioning from the unicast to the broadcast scenario. As shown in Fig. 10(b), the *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes continue to outperform the *RM*, *IRC*, and *Baseline* schemes also in the broadcast scenario. The semantic schemes allow vehicles to communicate more efficiently by significantly reducing the average number of exogenous variables needed to maximize the semantic value of the transmitted messages and accomplish the communication goal. The *Ideal Semantic* and *Semantic* schemes achieve a 2x and 1.8x improvement in SE performance (hence, in communication efficiency), respectively, compared to the *RM* scheme in the broadcast scenario (Fig. 10(b)). Their gain over the *Baseline* and *IRC* schemes increases by up to 2.8x and 2.4x (Fig. 10(b)). It is worth noting that the increase in the number of communicating vehicles also benefits the *RM* scheme over the *Baseline* and *IRC* schemes in the broadcast scenario, as *RM* leverages the increased redundancy and reduces the average number of variables per message, ultimately increasing its SE (Fig. 7(b) vs Fig. 10(b)). In contrast, the *Baseline* scheme does not curate the

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content of the transmitted messages and the *IRC* scheme does not fully exploit the increased redundancy. As a result, their SE performance deteriorates as the number of communicating vehicles and redundancy levels increase.

VII. CONCLUSION

The large-scale deployment of CAVs that will drive the digital transformation of transportation systems towards CCAM will lead to a substantial increase in the volume of data exchanged over V2X networks, potentially challenging their communication efficiency and scalability. To address these challenges, this paper introduces a semantic and task-oriented communication paradigm where information is transmitted based on its relevance (or semantic value) for the intended receivers. We evaluate this paradigm in the V2X domain as it offers a unique ecosystem for developing semantic communications.

Our study demonstrates that semantic and task-oriented V2X communications can accomplish the V2X communication goal more efficiently than existing V2X solutions in both unicast and broadcast scenarios. By focusing on the transmission of relevant information, semantic and task-oriented V2X communications increase the semantic value of the messages delivered to the intended receivers while reducing the overall volume of transmitted data. In our evaluation, semantic and task-oriented V2X communications achieve nearly a two-fold improvement in communication efficiency by halving the communication resources needed by each transmitting vehicle to deliver the relevant information to the intended receivers. Our study also highlights the importance of accurately estimating the context-dependent relevance of information for intended receivers to fully harness the potential of semantic V2X communications, with notable differences observed between unicast and broadcast scenarios. Broadcast V2X communications increase the number of communicating vehicles but also enriches the amount of contextual information shared across the network. This additional information improves the accuracy of relevance estimation, enabling semantic and task-oriented V2X communications to effectively identify the most relevant information, maximize the semantic value of transmitted messages, and reduce bandwidth consumption. Broadcast V2X communications increase the number of intended receivers compared to unicast communications, potentially increasing the amount of information per message. However, the advantages of an increased availability of contextual information outweigh any drawbacks from serving multiple receivers, and semantic V2X communications are significantly more efficient than existing solutions in achieving V2X communication goals also in broadcast scenarios.

Our study has highlighted key research challenges towards the development of semantic and task-oriented V2X communications. In particular, the study underscores the importance – and complexity – of a correct context understanding and of an accurate estimation of the relevance of the information for the intended receivers. These are major research challenges in V2X due to the dynamic nature of the

driving environment, and a complex endeavor that will require the generation of knowledge able to capture the fundamental and constituent relationships and correlations between driving environment elements by processing and interpreting contextual information. Future work includes analyzing the scalability of the envisioned semantic and task-oriented V2X communication paradigm in larger-scale broadcast scenarios.

REFERENCES

- [1] M.C. Lucas-Estañ *et al.*, “Direct-V2X Support with 5G Network-Based Communications: Performance, Challenges and Solutions,” *IEEE Network*, vol. 37, no. 4, pp. 200-207, July/August 2023.
- [2] CAR 2 CAR Communication Consortium, “Guidance for day 2 and beyond roadmap,” C2C-CC White Paper no. 2072, July 2021.
- [3] C. Shannon and W. Weaver, “The Mathematical Theory of Communication,” University of Illinois Press, 1962.
- [4] M. Sepulcre *et al.*, “LTE-V2X Scalability and Spectrum Requirements to support Multiple V2X Services,” in Proc. of IEEE VTC2024-Fall, 7-10 October 2023, Washington DC, USA.
- [5] H. Xie *et al.*, “Deep Learning Enabled Semantic Communication Systems,” in *IEEE Trans. on Signal Proc.*, vol. 69, pp. 2663-2675, 2021.
- [6] Z. Weng and Z. Qin, “Semantic Communication Systems for Speech Transmission,” in *IEEE JSAC*, vol. 39, no. 8, pp. 2434-2444, Aug. 2021.
- [7] J. Xu, T. -Y. Tung, B. Ai, W. Chen, Y. Sun and D. Gündüz, “Deep Joint Source-Channel Coding for Semantic Communications,” in *IEEE Communications Magazine*, vol. 61, no. 11, pp. 42-48, November 2023.
- [8] P. Jiang *et al.*, “Wireless Semantic Communications for Video Conferencing,” in *IEEE JSAC*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 230-244, Jan. 2023.
- [9] J. M. Gimenez-Guzman *et al.*, “Semantic V2X Communications for Image Transmission in 6G Systems,” in *IEEE Network*, Early Access.
- [10] R. D. Yates *et al.*, “Age of Information: An Introduction and Survey,” in *IEEE JSAC*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 1183-1210, May 2021.
- [11] A. Maatouk *et al.*, “The Age of Incorrect Information: An Enabler of Semantics-Empowered Communication,” in *IEEE Transactions on Wireless Communications*, vol. 22, no. 4, pp. 2621-2635, April 2023.
- [12] R. A. Howard, “Information Value Theory,” in *IEEE Transactions on Systems Science and Cybernetics*, vol. 2, no. 1, pp. 22-26, Aug. 1966.
- [13] D. Gündüz *et al.*, “Beyond Transmitting Bits: Context, Semantics, and Task-Oriented Communications,” in *IEEE JSAC*, vol. 41, no. 1, pp. 5-41, Jan. 2023.
- [14] D. Sperber and D. Wilson, “Relevance: Communications and Cognition,” Blackwell Publishers Inc. 1995.
- [15] G. Thandavarayan *et al.*, “Cooperative Perception for Connected and Automated Vehicles: Evaluation and Impact of Congestion Control,” in *IEEE Access*, vol. 8, pp. 197665-197683, 2020.
- [16] T. Higuchi *et al.*, “Value-Anticipating V2V Communications for Cooperative Perception,” in Proc. IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium, Paris, France, 2019, pp. 1947-1952.
- [17] G. Thandavarayan *et al.*, “Redundancy Mitigation in Cooperative Perception for Connected and Automated Vehicles,” in Proc. IEEE VTC2020-Spring, Antwerp, Belgium, 2020, pp. 1-5.
- [18] J. Löhdefink *et al.*, “Focussing Learned Image Compression to Semantic Classes for V2X Applications,” in Proc. 2020 IEEE Intelligent Vehicles Symposium (IV), Las Vegas, NV, USA, 2020, pp. 1641-1648.
- [19] Q. Pan *et al.*, “Image Segmentation Semantic Communication over Internet of Vehicles,” in Proc. 2023 IEEE WCNC, UK, 2023, pp. 1-6.
- [20] W. Xu *et al.*, “Semantic Communication for the Internet of Vehicles: A Multiuser Cooperative Approach,” in *IEEE Vehicular Technology Magazine*, vol. 18, no. 1, pp. 100-109, March 2023.
- [21] M. Giordani *et al.*, “A Framework to Assess Value of Information in Future Vehicular Networks,” in Proc. 1st ACM MobiHoc Workshop TOP-Cars '19, 2019, ACM, New York, NY, USA, pp. 31-36.
- [22] W. Wang *et al.*, “Value Matters: A Novel Value of Information-Based Resource Scheduling Method for CAVs,” in *IEEE Transactions on Vehicular Technology*, vol. 73, no. 6, pp. 8720-8735, June 2024.
- [23] ETSI, “Intelligent Transport System (ITS); Vehicular Communications; Basic Set of Applications; Collective Perception Service; Release 2,” ETSI TS 103 324 V2.1.1, June 2023.
- [24] A. W. Harrington and P. S. Rogers, “What is “communication context”?”, University of Michigan library, paper no. 584, 1988.